

LEARN OF STREPTOCOCCUS IN THE COMPOSITION OF ORAL MICROFLORA IN INDIVIDUALS RECOVERING FROM COVID-19

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ABSTRACT: *in this study, oral microbiology and microflora examination, a study of its relationship with COVID-19. To study the strangeness between high bacterial foci in the head of the son and complications after the virus and how the risk of complications of COVID-19 can be reduced in improving the head of the son.*{9,11,13,2}

Keywords: *COVID-19, Staphylococcus, Streptococcus, mitis, mutans, periodontal.*

Material and methods: in this study, the complications of COVID-19 observed among those with periodontal disease, in which the head of the son was in poor condition, were studied. Among the population, patients recovered from the coronavirus were selected, and the microbiology and microflora of their soniz chief were studied to analyze its relationship with COVID-19. In the village of Uklan, Oqdarya District of Samarkand region, 14 patients recovered from coronavirus were selected, and 4 of them are men and women from 40 years old, the rest are around 20-40 years old. From the lunch and dental part of the oral head of the selected patients, a smear was taken with the help of strel tampons and a gram-positive dye and bacteriological examination was carried out. The resulting ointments were sown and studied in sugar broth, whey agar and sugar Agar. Morphological structure of 33 strains of isolated streptococci, determined. {1,3,4,6,7,16}

Research results: 6 out of 14 examined patients (42.85%) were identified Streptococcus mitis in 13 strains and Streptococcus mutans in 18 strains out of 8 (57.15%). Of the identified strains, none of the toxins hemulating erythrocytes were detected. In addition to him, caries was detected in 11 (78.6%) over 30 years of age of patients undergoing research. {21,22,24,} An increase in the number of inflammatory symptoms, bacteria and neutrophil-lymphocytes was also observed in 50 percent of infected patients.

In conclusion, in those who have recovered as a result of the SARS-Cov-2019 virus, it is necessary to maintain, clean the oral hygiene. These measures are important for patients with diabetes, heart disease, people with hypertension. In addition, the presence of bacterial hyperfunction in patients who have recovered from it indicates that they are distributors of infection.

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